

Review Article

Pharmacological Agents in the Management of Postpartum Hemorrhage (PPH); a Clinical Review

Olorunfemi Oludele Owa*^{1,2}

¹Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Federal Medical Centre, Owo, Nigeria

²Department of Pharmacology, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, Nigeria

Background: Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) is a leading cause of maternal mortality worldwide, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Effective pharmacological interventions are critical for prevention, timely management and favourable outcomes. **Objective:** This review evaluates the current pharmacological agents used in the prevention and treatment of PPH, their mechanisms of action, indications, efficacy, and safety profiles. **Methods:** A comprehensive literature search was conducted using PubMed, Cochrane Library, and WHO databases to identify relevant studies and guidelines from 2000 to 2024. **Results:** Uterotonics remain the mainstay of PPH management, with oxytocin being the first-line agent. Other agents include misoprostol, ergometrine, carboprost and recently carbetocin importantly in the low socioeconomic settings. Tranexamic acid has emerged as a vital adjunct in controlling bleeding and preventing PPH-related maternal death. The selection of agents depends on availability, contraindications, and the clinical setting. The future directions in the Pharmacological Management of Postpartum Hemorrhage (PPH) such as Oxytocin Receptor Genotyping, Biomarker-Guided Fibrinogen Replacement and Viscoelastic Testing (TEG/ROTEM)-Guided Therapy were extensively discussed. **Conclusion:** A multimodal pharmacologic approach, tailored to individual risk factors and resource availability, is essential for reducing PPH-related morbidity and mortality. Early administration of uterotonics and adjunct therapies like tranexamic acid is key in both prevention and treatment.

Keywords: Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH).

INTRODUCTION

Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) is defined as blood loss of ≥ 500 mL after vaginal birth or ≥ 1000 mL after cesarean section.¹ It is a major cause of maternal mortality, especially in low-resource settings like sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia. PPH can be classified as: Primary (early) – within 24 hours after delivery. Secondary (late) – between 24 hours and 6 weeks postpartum.^{1,2} The most common cause is uterine atony, accounting for approximately 70-80% of cases.² Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) accounts for approximately 27% of maternal deaths worldwide, with the burden disproportionately high in low-resource settings.¹⁻³ However, modern definitions increasingly emphasize quantitative blood loss using calibrated drapes and clinical instability via

continuous vital signs evaluation, recognizing that visual estimation underestimates hemorrhage severity.⁴ While surgical interventions and uterine tamponade are sometimes necessary, pharmacological management is the first-line and most accessible treatment, particularly in resource-limited settings.^{3,5}

The pathophysiology of PPH

The pathophysiology of PPH is multifactorial and can be categorized into the “4 Ts”: **Tone (uterine atony), Tissue (retained placenta), Trauma (genital tract injury), Thrombin (coagulopathy)**. Uterine atony accounts for approximately 70–80% of cases, making pharmacologic uterotonic therapy central to management.^{5,6} The molecular and cellular

mechanisms of uterine atony: The normal physiology of hemostasis following child birth is such that, after placental separation, approximately 500–800 mL/min of blood flows through uterine spiral arteries.⁶ Hemostasis followed some notable physiological changes aided by uterotonics which include myometrial contraction (living ligatures mechanism), compression of spiral arteries, local platelet aggregation and activation of coagulation cascade. Myometrial contraction is calcium-dependent and mediated by oxytocin receptor activation, phospholipase C stimulation, IP₃-mediated intracellular calcium release, and actin–myosin cross-bridge cycling.⁶ Uterine atony therefore, represents failure of effective myometrial contraction. Contributing factors to atony include, oxytocin receptor desensitization after prolonged labor or high-dose oxytocin infusion, myometrial overstretch (multiple gestation, polyhydramnios), magnesium sulfate-induced smooth muscle relaxation, inflammatory cytokine-mediated myometrial dysfunction, hypoxia-induced ATP depletion. Other interesting pathophysiology for further research suggests downregulation of oxytocin receptor density, altered connexin-43 expression (gap junction impairment) and reduced myosin light chain kinase activation. These cellular disruptions impair coordinated uterine contraction, resulting in persistent bleeding.^{6,7} Coagulation abnormalities and hemostatic failure may also result in severe bleeding after delivery.⁸ Severe PPH may rapidly lead to consumptive coagulopathy, dilutional coagulopathy, hypofibrinogenemia, disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC). Fibrinogen is the earliest coagulation factor to decline in massive obstetric hemorrhage. Levels < 2 g/L are strongly predictive of severe PPH progression.⁹ The pregnancy state is normally a hypercoagulable state, characterized by elevated fibrinogen, increased factors VII, VIII, X and reduced protein S.^{8,10} However, severe hemorrhage overwhelms compensatory mechanisms, leading to impaired clot stability, hyperfibrinolysis (plasmin activation) and microvascular bleeding. This pathophysiology explained the pharmacologic role of antifibrinolytics (tranexamic acid).¹¹

Pharmacological Agents in PPH Management

Uterotonics are a cornerstone in the prevention and treatment of postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), which is one of the leading causes of maternal morbidity and mortality worldwide. PPH is commonly caused by uterine atony—failure of the uterus to contract effectively after delivery—accounting for up to 80% of cases. Common uterotonics include oxytocin, ergometrine/methylergometrine, misoprostol, carboprost tromethamine, carbetocin. Other pharmacological agent like tranexamic acid has shown to be very important in the prevention of PPH-related maternal death.⁹⁻¹⁴ Oxytocin is a nonapeptide synthesized in the hypothalamus and released from the posterior pituitary. It binds to Gq protein-coupled oxytocin receptors (OXTR), activating phospholipase C, inositol triphosphate (IP₃), intracellular calcium release, calmodulin activation, myosin light chain kinase stimulation.⁶ The activation of this cascade results in rhythmic uterine contractions. Oxytocin plays a crucial role in childbirth, lactation, and maternal behavior. It is also widely used in clinical obstetrics.⁸ It stimulates rhythmic contractions of the uterus during labor and increases in concentration at term to help initiate labor. At birth it stimulates uterine smooth muscle contractions by binding to oxytocin receptors. It is given after delivery to contract the uterus and reduce bleeding. Oxytocin is the first-line uterotonic agent recommended by WHO for PPH prevention and treatment.² The dosage of 10 IU IM or IV after delivery; continuous infusion may follow. The onset of action depends on route of administration; for intravenous route, onset is within 1 minute and intramuscular route is 3–5 minutes with the half-life of 1–6 minutes (short-acting) the undergo rapid hepatic and renal metabolism. Oxytocin is the standard uterotonic used for prevention, but it requires cold-chain storage, which limits its utility in low-resource settings. Oxytocin requires refrigeration at 2–8°C and cold chain transportation, less effective if uterus is already atonic. It is recommended as first-line by WHO and FIGO.² Side effect include hypotension (especially with rapid IV bolus), water intoxication (with high doses due to antidiuretic effect), nausea, vomiting. Limitations to its use include receptor desensitization, heat instability and need for cold chain.¹⁰ **Ergometrine** and **Methylergometrine** (a semi-synthetic derivative of ergometrine) are **uterotonic agents** used in the prevention and treatment of **postpartum**

hemorrhage (PPH), particularly when uterine atony is the cause.³ They act on alpha (α) -**adrenergic, dopaminergic, and serotonergic receptors**, leading to **sustained uterine contractions** (in contrast to the rhythmic contractions of oxytocin). Constriction of uterine and peripheral blood vessels reduces blood loss. The drugs act on smooth muscle of the uterus via alpha-adrenergic and serotonergic receptors. The dosage is 0.2 mg IM or slow IV; repeated every 2–4 hours as needed. Its hemodynamic effects include systemic vasoconstriction that may precipitate severe hypertension, coronary vasospasm, and stroke (rare but documented). It is contraindicated in preeclampsia and chronic hypertension. It is second-line agent after oxytocin failure and more effective in cases of uterine atony because it causes sustained contraction. It can result in nausea, vomiting and elevated blood pressure. It is useful in uterine atony resistant to oxytocin.³ Misoprostol is a **prostaglandin E1 (PGE1) analogue** used for **prevention and treatment of postpartum hemorrhage (PPH)**, especially in **low-resource settings** due to its **low cost, heat stability, and non-injectable routes**.⁷ It is appropriate in setting with less expertise. It is low onset and long acting. It stimulates uterine smooth muscle contraction by binding to prostaglandin receptors, also enhances uterine tone and reduces blood loss from the placental site. The dosage 600–800 mcg for prevention or 800-1000mcg for treatment respectively.^{7,8} It can be administered orally, sublingually, or rectally. Sublingual (preferred: rapid absorption), Rectal (used if vomiting or unconscious), oral (less preferred due to slower onset). Its onset of action is 8–15 minutes and duration of action is 1–2 hours. Its side effects include fever, shivering, diarrhea and abdominal cramps. It is particularly useful where oxytocin is unavailable or unstable.⁴ **Carboprost Tromethamine (15-methyl PGF₂ α)** is a synthetic analogue of **prostaglandin F2-alpha (PGF₂ α)** used as **uterotonic agent** for the treatment of **postpartum hemorrhage (PPH)** due to uterine atony when other methods (like oxytocin or ergometrine) have failed. Carboprost stimulates uterine smooth muscle contraction by binding to prostaglandin F receptors and increases intracellular calcium, helping to reduce blood loss by promoting uterine tone and reducing uterine bleeding. It is used at 250 mcg IM every 15–90 minutes; max 2 mg.^{12,13} It is contraindicated in asthma, renal/liver disease. Its

side effects nausea, diarrhea, bronchospasm. It is very effective in refractory cases.⁵ Tranexamic acid (TXA) is a synthetic derivative of the amino acid lysine and an antifibrinolytic agent. It works by inhibiting plasminogen activation and preventing the breakdown of fibrin clots (fibrinolysis), thus promoting clot stability and reducing bleeding.⁹ TXA is used as an adjunct in the management of primary postpartum hemorrhage, particularly when bleeding is suspected to be due to trauma or uterine atony.¹¹ Tranexamic Acid (TXA) competitively inhibits plasminogen binding to fibrin, preventing conversion to plasmin and stabilizing clots. It increased tissue plasminogen activator (tPA), accelerated fibrinolysis and clot destabilization. TXA counters this hyperfibrinolytic state of pregnancy.^{11,14} The landmark WOMAN Trial demonstrated 31% reduction in death due to bleeding if given within 3 hours and no significant increase in thromboembolic events.⁹ This shifted global guidelines to recommend early TXA administration alongside uterotonic. It is most effective when administered early, preferably within 3 hours of birth. The dosage is 1 gram IV over 10 minutes (not exceeding 1 ml per minute). A second dose of 1 gram may be given if bleeding continues or restarts after 30 minutes. TXA reduces death from bleeding when used early.^{6,9} The **WOMAN Trial** (World Maternal Antifibrinolytic Trial) was a **landmark, randomized, placebo-controlled trial** that evaluated the efficacy of TXA in women with PPH. It is multinational, multicenter trial across 21 countries over **20,000 women** with clinically diagnosed PPH participated. TXA significantly reduced death due to bleeding if given within 3 hours of childbirth. The relative risk reduction in bleeding deaths by 31% when administered early. There was no increase in thromboembolic events and did not increase the risk of pulmonary embolism, deep vein thrombosis, or stroke. There is greater benefit of TXA when used early and this benefit was time-dependent—maximum effect seen when administered within 3 hours.⁹ TXA did not reduce the need for hysterectomy, possibly because hysterectomies were often decided immediately upon diagnosis. TXA is now included in **WHO guidelines** and several **national protocols** for the **first-line management of PPH**. It is most useful **in all cases of PPH**, regardless of the cause (trauma, atony, retained placenta). **Early administration** is crucial, **should not wait** for

second-line interventions. There is guideline update by WHO which recommends routine use of TXA in PPH alongside uterotonics.^{4,7} Other hemostatic agents; fibrinogen replacement is a modality of management in PPH. The low fibrinogen is an early marker of severe PPH. Replacement can be via cryoprecipitate and or fibrinogen concentrate. This will improve the clot strength and reduces ongoing bleeding. Also, another modality reserved for refractory hemorrhage is recombinant activated factor VII. It acts by activating factor X independent of tissue factor and promotes thrombin burst. The hemostatic agents are expensive and has higher thrombotic risk.¹¹

New and Emerging Therapies

Heat-stable carbetocin (HSC) is a synthetic nonapeptide, long-acting oxytocin analog designed to remain effective without refrigeration, offering a potential alternative to the first line uterotonic oxytocin.¹⁵ The WHO CHAMPION Trial, a multicentre, double-blind, randomized, non-inferiority trial of Heat-stable carbetocin 100 mcg IM or IV versus Oxytocin 10 IU IM or IV in 10 countries across Africa, Asia, and Latin America with 29,645 women delivering vaginally showed that the Heat-stable carbetocin is non-inferior to oxytocin for PPH prevention after vaginal birth and offers logistical benefits by eliminating the need for cold storage. Its adoption in LMICs could significantly improve access to effective PPH prevention and reduce maternal mortality.¹⁵ Carbetocin binds to oxytocin receptors on uterine smooth muscle cells. It stimulates rhythmic uterine contractions, increasing uterine tone. This promotes placental separation and reduces uterine bleeding by compressing uterine blood vessels. It is more resistant to enzymatic degradation, giving it a longer duration of action than oxytocin. It has a rapid onset; within 2 minutes (IV) and 5 minutes (IM), reaches peak plasma level in 5 minutes and duration of action is about 60minutes. Compared with oxytocin with half-life of ~4–10 min, carbetocin is 40–60 minutes.¹⁵ It remains stable at 30°C for at least 3 years, unlike oxytocin which degrades with heat.

Other Considerations:

Combination therapy is often, more than one uterotonic is used if bleeding persists. Blood transfusion and volume replacement:

Should accompany pharmacologic therapy in severe cases. EMOTIVE is a practical mnemonic developed by the WHO and global maternal health experts to guide effective, rapid, team-based management of PPH. It emphasizes the “bundled approach” — doing key interventions together, without delay.¹⁶ EMOTIVE stands for E — Evaluate blood loss early (using calibrated drapes), M — Massage the uterus (uterine massage to stimulate contraction), O — Oxytocics (administer first-line uterotonics e.g., oxytocin/carbetocin, ergometrine or misoprostol), T — Tranexamic acid (TXA within 3 hours of birth if bleeding continues), I — IV fluids (start resuscitation, maintain circulation), V — Vitals monitoring (frequent checks, signs of shock), E — Escalate when needed (call for help, surgical interventions, refer).¹⁶ The EMOTIVE bundle means applying these interventions simultaneously or in rapid succession, rather than step-by-step only after other measures fail. The evidence shows that bundled, team-based, proactive care reduces severe PPH and maternal mortality. The focus therefore, is on early action to prevent progression to severe bleeding and shock.^{9,16} Blood transfusion and volume replacement may accompany pharmacologic therapy in severe cases. Non-Pharmacologic Measures (if drugs fail): Uterine massage, balloon tamponade, surgical interventions (e.g., B-Lynch suture, hysterectomy) may be applicable.^{12,13} Combination Therapy and Guidelines; the WHO, FIGO, RCOG and SOGON recommend a stepwise pharmacologic approach. Combination therapy (e.g., oxytocin + TXA) shows improved outcomes in severe PPH. In settings lacking cold chain storage, carbetocin is preferred in prevention of PPH.¹³ Challenges in Low-Resource Settings is the inadequate availability of cold-chain dependent oxytocin, thus, the use of carbetocin should be encouraged. There is also limited access to TXA and carboprost. A delay in recognition and diagnosing of PPH due to visual estimation of blood loss.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ The importance of training health workers on use and side effect monitoring of pharmacological agents in prevention and treatment of PPH cannot be overemphasized.^{12,13}

Future Directions in the Pharmacological Management of Postpartum Hemorrhage (PPH)

Emerging precision-medicine strategies aim to move PPH management from protocol-driven algorithms toward individualized, pathophysiology-targeted therapy. Three promising directions include oxytocin receptor genotyping, biomarker-guided fibrinogen replacement, and viscoelastic-guided hemostatic therapy.²⁰ Oxytocin Receptor Genotyping; the pathophysiological rationale of oxytocin receptor genotyping thrives on the premise that oxytocin action depends on binding to the oxytocin receptor (OXTR), a G-protein coupled receptor expressed on myometrial smooth muscle. Receptor activation increases intracellular calcium via the phospholipase C-IP₃ pathway, triggering coordinated uterine contraction.²¹⁻²⁴ Variability in uterine responsiveness to oxytocin may be partly explained by genetic polymorphisms in the OXTR gene, receptor desensitization after prolonged oxytocin exposure, downregulation of receptor density following labor induction or augmentation, obesity-associated altered receptor signaling. Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in the OXTR gene have been associated with differential oxytocin sensitivity and labor dynamics. Some women demonstrate oxytocin resistance, requiring higher infusion rates during labor and potentially showing reduced uterine tone postpartum.²¹ Clinical Implications in future strategies may include: Pre-delivery OXTR genotyping to identify high-risk women, individualized oxytocin dosing regimens, early use of alternative uterotonics (e.g., prostaglandins or ergot alkaloids) in predicted poor responders and development of novel oxytocin receptor agonists with reduced desensitization. Large-scale genomic-pharmacodynamic correlation studies are needed before routine implementation of this genotyping is being implemented.²²

Biomarker-Guided Fibrinogen Replacement

The pathophysiological rationale is that fibrinogen is the first coagulation factor to decline during major obstetric hemorrhage due to dilutional coagulopathy, hyperfibrinolysis, consumption from disseminated intravascular coagulation and placental tissue factor-mediated thrombin generation. In pregnancy,

physiological fibrinogen levels are elevated (approximately 4–6 g/L).²⁵ Importantly, fibrinogen levels <2.0 g/L during PPH strongly predict progression to severe hemorrhage. In Biomarker-Guided Strategy, early plasma fibrinogen measurement can guide the decision. This will target fibrinogen concentrate administration, cryoprecipitate replacement and avoidance of empiric massive transfusion. A precision approach would therefore, measure fibrinogen early in active PPH, replace fibrinogen when levels fall below critical thresholds (e.g., <2–3 g/L) and reassess dynamically. The advantages will include reduced unnecessary blood product exposure, faster correction of hypofibrinogenemia, potential reduction in hysterectomy rates and improved resource utilization. Future research should define optimal replacement thresholds and compare fibrinogen concentrate versus cryoprecipitate in obstetric populations.^{20,25}

Viscoelastic Testing (TEG/ROTEM)-Guided Therapy

Another modality based on pathophysiological rationale of Standard coagulation tests (PT, aPTT) are slow (laboratory turnaround delays), plasma-based (ignore platelet contribution), poor predictors of bleeding severity. In contrast, *viscoelastic testing* such as Thromboelastography (TEG) and Rotational thromboelastometry (ROTEM) provides real-time, whole-blood assessment of clot formation, strength, and fibrinolysis.²⁶ These tests assess Clot initiation time (coagulation factor activity), Clot amplitude/strength (platelets + fibrinogen) and Clot lysis (hyperfibrinolysis). TEG/ROTEM-guided algorithms can allow targeted fibrinogen replacement when clot amplitude is low, platelet transfusion when clot strength reflects thrombocytopenia, early identification of hyperfibrinolysis prompting tranexamic acid use and reduced unnecessary plasma transfusion. Studies suggest reduced transfusion volume and faster correction of coagulopathy compared with fixed-ratio massive transfusion protocols.^{25,27} The future model of PPH care may combine early TXA administration, real-time viscoelastic monitoring, biomarker-guided fibrinogen supplementation and algorithm-based escalation to interventional radiology or surgery. Implementation

challenges include cost, training, and availability in low-resource settings.

Integrated Precision Model of PPH Management

A future precision-obstetric model may therefore involve; Pre-delivery risk stratification (OXTR genotyping and Clinical risk scoring).^{22,28} Early hemorrhage phase (Immediate uterotonics, Early tranexamic acid, Baseline fibrinogen measurement, TEG/ROTEM assessment) and Targeted escalation (Fibrinogen concentrate if hypofibrinogenemia, Platelets if clot strength reduced and Avoidance of empiric transfusion).²⁰ Research opportunity in pharmacotherapy of PPH include large multicenter RCTs evaluating genotype-guided uterotonic therapy, threshold trials for fibrinogen concentrate in PPH, cost-effectiveness studies of universal viscoelastic monitoring, integration of artificial intelligence into PPH prediction algorithms. The next decade of PPH pharmacological management is likely to transition from standardized uterotonic protocols to **mechanism-guided precision obstetrics**. Oxytocin receptor genotyping may optimize uterotonic responsiveness,²² fibrinogen biomarkers may guide hemostatic replacement,^{20,28} and viscoelastic testing may enable dynamic correction of coagulopathy.²⁶ Together, these strategies promise improved maternal outcomes, reduced transfusion exposure, and more rational pharmacotherapy.²⁹

CONCLUSION

The pharmacological management of PPH is a critical intervention that saves lives. A tailored approach utilizing oxytocin, HSC, misoprostol, and tranexamic acid — according to clinical presentation and resource availability — is necessary. Ongoing research into new agents and protocols, along with investment in drug accessibility, will further reduce maternal mortality from PPH.

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